

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF REGULATING THE ACTIVITY OF INSURANCE COMPANIES

Islamov Shukhratjon Tuychibayevich

Tashkent Financial Institute "Corporate
finance and securities"

senior teacher of the department

shuhrat.islamov@inbox.ru

Abstract. This scientific thesis describes the scientific basis and necessity of regulating the activities of insurance companies. In recent years, the reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the development of insurance sectors and the trends in the development of the insurance market have been analyzed. In international practice, studies have been carried out on the main directions of state regulation of the insurance system.

Key words: insurance, financial instrument, investment, deposits, capital, financial stability, insurance reserves, standards, financial risk.

The role of investment activities in ensuring the financial stability of insurance companies is of great importance. In recent years, the number of insurance companies in our country has increased, as well as their investment opportunities and potential in the capital market. The financial stability of insurance companies allows to ensure the continuity of their activity under any conditions, to prevent risks regarding obligations to the insured, and to realize additional investment opportunities. Various problems related to ensuring the financial stability of insurance companies are prevented through the level of profitability, capital adequacy, liquidity ratio and the amount of reserves created by insurance companies. According to the results of 2022, a total of 41 insurance companies are operating in

the Republic, of which 8 are specialized in life insurance. Their total charter capital in 2021 will be 1589.8 billion. amounted to 1884.1 billion soums, by the end of 2022 it increased by 18.5% or 1884.1 billion soums. Also, the participation of insurance companies in the capital market has a special place, and in the following years, the participation of insurance companies in the securities market has a growing tendency. If in 2021 the number of insurance brokers was 5, by the end of 2022 their number will reach 7. By the end of 2022, the volume of total investments of insurers increased by 26.8% compared to the same period last year and reached 4751.7 billion soums (Table 1).

Table 1 shows that the main areas of investment are related to deposits and real estate. If we analyze both areas, during the analyzed period, the volume of investments in deposits increased by 31.1%, and the volume of investments related to real estate increased by 45.1%. As one of the important aspects, it can be noted that in 2022, the volume of other investments increased by almost 5 times compared to the previous year, which is considered to be an increase in the diversification of investment activities by insurance companies. In 2021, the amount of investment in securities amounted to 1,095.9 billion soums, and by 2022, this indicator increased by 17.5% or reached 1,287.9 billion soums. indicates that the company's participation in the stock market is increasing. The ability to collect financial cash flows and direct them to the development of the economy makes insurance companies a powerful institutional investor. In developed countries, insurance company asset placement standards, maximum and minimum quotas of insurance reserves, and a list of assets covering insurance reserves have been developed.

1-Table

Investment activity of insurers ¹

№	Indicator name	2021 year	2022 year	
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¹ <https://imda.uz/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/2022-yillik.pdf> - ma'lumotlari asosida tayyorlandi.

		billion sums	In % of total	billion sums	In % of total	Change, %
1	Total investment, including::	3746,6	100	4751,7	100	+26,8
2	Deposits	2208,5	58,9	2896,6	61,0	+31,2
3	Securities	1095,9	29,3	1287,9	27,1	+17,5
4	Loans	47,4	1,3	60,7	1,3	+28,1
5	Real estate	247,3	6,6	358,9	7,6	+45,1
6	Participation in the charter fund of organizations	142,2	3,8	118,2	2,5	-16,9
7	Other investments	5,1	0,1	29,2	0,6	+471,1

The developed standards are regulated depending on the level of economic development, the state of financial markets, and national traditions. Investment directions of insurance companies are determined separately in the field of life insurance and separately in other general insurance networks. In the European Union, the United Kingdom, and the United States, the responsibility for regulating the insurance market is somewhat divided between state, local, and regional authorities. Each state in the United States has independent insurance regulatory bodies. EU countries have their own regulatory bodies but follow directives that are common to each of them. Features of foreign experience in the formation of investment policies of insurance companies are presented in Table 2 below. There are two approaches (schools) of state regulation of investment policy in foreign countries, which are reflected in the state's role in investment activities and participation (influence) in determining tariff rates. The first approach is the

American school, which says that the underlying activity can be unprofitable, but such losses can be compensated by the income from the investment activity. The second is the approach of the European school, in which, in addition to the investment activity, the main net insurance activity must be profitable.

2-Table

Features of state control of investment activities of insurance companies in foreign countries²

Countries	Features of investment policy formation of insurance companies
USA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A certain part of the income is invested in the territory of the state. 2. Investment conditions are established in the prescribed manner. 3. The average composition of assets is determined. 4. Insurance companies provide investment loans to industrial enterprises for a period of 15-20 years.
Great Britain	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rules for the placement of financial resources are established. 2. The average composition of life insurance assets is determined. 3. There is a state investment policy program. 4. The value of the investment portfolio is constantly monitored.
Germany	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The law on placement of reserves of insurance companies applies. 2. Investing principles apply (safety, profitability, liquidity, diversification, etc.). 3. Joylashtirish shakllari va ular bo'yicha cheklovlar o'rnatiladi. 4. Aktivlar ishonchli boshqaruvga o'tkaziladi.

In practice, long-term investment in the insurance portfolio is more profitable than medium- and short-term investment. Long-term investments, such as real

² Second annual business risk report - insurance / Oxford Analytical / Ernst& Young. 2014. P. 4. (murojat sanasi 2019 yil 12 mart)

estate, medium- and short-term investments include stocks, bonds, bank deposits, and temporary free funds in a company account. However, it should be taken into account that long-term investments bring a lot of income, while medium- and short-term investments are considered liquid when the need to fulfill payment obligations arises. Taking into account the experiences of developed countries, measures to further improve insurance activities in Uzbekistan are creating the necessary conditions for the rapid development of the insurance market. In our country, the state has been performing the task of the main reformer in ensuring that the activities of insurance companies can meet international requirements and become a competitive industry. The adoption of a number of regulatory documents related to insurance activities in our country serves to increase the quality of insurance services and increase the confidence of the population in insurance services.

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